

Stress Vulnerability and Academic Performance among Management Students of UM TAGUM College: Basis for Enhancement Program

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Abstract: The main objective of this study was to investigate if there is a significant relationship between stress vulnerability and academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College. The sampling technique used was the random sampling wherein 95 management students of UM Tagum College served as respondents. This study used the quantitative non-experimental research design using correlational technique with mean and pearson-r as statistical tools. A validated survey questionnaire was used as principal data collection instrument. Results revealed that the level of stress vulnerability was moderate, while the level of academic performance was low. Meanwhile, findings showed that there was no significant relationship between stress vulnerability and academic performance. This means that, there might be other factors aside from stress that relates to the increase or decrease of the academic performance of the management students. Finally, though there's no correlation that exist, the researcher still proposed a program design that will target on lessening stress and improving the academic performance of the students (see Appendix A).

Keywords: Academic Performance, Enhancement Program, Human Resource Management, Stress Vulnerability, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

Schools, universities, and colleges have no value without students. Learners are the most basic resources for any organization. The social economic and financial advancement of the nation was explicitly connected with learner's academic performance. The academic achievement of students shows vital part on becoming effective and efficient graduates which subsequently become an asset in this country which can be beneficial in this nation's social and economic development (Ali et al., 2009).

Furthermore, it was emphasized in the Organizational Behavior book of Robbins (1998) that a high-stress level or even an adequate amount sustained over a long period eventually takes its toll, that may result in the decline of the performance. Also, it was mentioned that stress experienced by the students in the school are the following: bombarded homework, student competition (peer pressure), teacher's failure to monitor student progress, financial constraints, poor relationship with other students, poor teaching strategy, and family problems among others. These stressors were categorized as environmental, economic, family and school factors (Fair brother & Warn, 2003; Taylara, 2012).

In the academe, the faculty members are the ones who have direct contact with the student, and each of them can detect the stress level of the students through observation in school. Causes of it may not all school related but can be from different factors other than academics. The study also shows that the degree of stress of college students vary by year level and gender that is why the interpersonal relationship of the faculty-student should be taken consideration because teachers are said to be their second parents. As the students step up every semester, the stress level also increases due to numerous academic commitments, financial constraints and being preoccupied with many things yet with poor time management. But, to other studies, this increase in stress can be addressed and reduced through effective time management and organized study habits (Misra et al., 2000). Thus, the faculty member's perception of student academic stress is important because they can help to be one of the stress relievers of the students.

A lot of college student find the academic experience very stressful, and one way for them to cope is by having a university counseling service and time management. In the research conducted abroad, 165 students completed a survey

questionnaire measuring their level of stress and grade point average (GPA) and two significant findings were found: Excellent Time Management was seen to be correlated with high academic performance, more excellent work and life satisfaction. Also, the positivity and self-efficacy of a students in school may lead them to become more loyal and committed to study and excel. Furthermore, an improved mood of the students can also lead to enhanced academic performance (Chemers, Hu & Garcia, 2001; Lumley & Provenzano, 2003).

On the other hand, student academic performance assessment has gotten important consideration in past researches. It is a testing part of scholarly writing, and educational literature since learner's performance is influenced by social, mental, financial, environmental and individual elements. UM Tagum College students are not exempted from this issue. Indeed, as per observation, a large portion of every class was working poorly in their performance, particularly in the department of business administration (as based in their final grades). Furthermore, in the study conducted by Akgun and Ciarrochi (2003) results revealed a negative correlation between stress and academic performance and by this, UM Tagum College students maybe right on blaming stress as one of the reasons for the decline in their performance.

Therefore, in this context, the researcher feels the need to conduct the study particularly assessing the level of stress vulnerability and academic performance of management students since it was directly observed that problematic students exist in this department, the basis was manifested in their grade/scores or through informal consultation or conversation. Proposal for appropriate interventions was also one of the main goals to address the problems. Performance usually is connected with burnout, and something must be done to realize what caused it and in how to oversee it legitimately.

In the light of these concerns, this study is undertaken. The primary objective of this study was to establish the significant relationship between stress vulnerability and academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following sub-questions: To assess the level of stress vulnerability among management students of UM Tagum College in terms of: family factors, financial factors; school factors; and environmental factors; To determine the level of academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College using GPA; To ascertain if there is a significant relationship between stress vulnerability and academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College.

The outcome of the study would give pertinent data to the entire UMTC students especially the School Administrators in implementing suitable enhancement program that encourage students to be progressive in their academic performance. Also, the results of the study enable Faculty members to have a deeper understanding of the student's family, environment, monetary and school-related issues which distress them. This study will likewise save as a basis for possible interventions intended to change learner's attitude, hence helping them adjust or adapt to the challenges of higher education. Ultimately, this study enables Students to realize how to manage their pressure and to appreciate the value of study habits and time management as espoused by their teachers.

II. METHOD

Presented below are the research steps and procedures that were taken by the researcher in this study. These include the Participants, Research Instruments, Design, and Procedure. Random sampling was used wherein 95 management students participated as respondents.

The primary tool used in the data gathering process was the survey questionnaire adapted from Taylara (2012). To acquire data efficiently that the level of stress vulnerability of management student was measured, the researcher contextualized the questionnaire that fit to the college students, since initially it was intended for elementary students. The said questionnaire dealt with four stressors (family, financial, school and environment) that student may experience. The management student's academic performance was measured based on its Grade Point Average (GPA) of the class.

The questionnaire consisted of statements measuring the respondents' stress vulnerability. The respondents checked the scale that expresses how they feel about the statements. Dawes (2008) mentioned that using 5-point Likert scale in this type of study can help the respondent easily assess the accounts based on their experiences.

This study utilized quantitative non-experimental design employing the correlational technique. This method helps to identify the relationship between two variables at least, and tries to examine the degree to which at least one or many relationships of some sort exist (Fraenkel, 2003).

The following steps were followed in gathering the data: Upon approval, the questionnaires were presented to the experts (at least a Master's degree holder in a related field) and grammarian for the modification and content validation of the survey questionnaire. Afterward, the questionnaires were administered personally by the researcher to the respondents of the study. Lastly, after the questionnaires were accomplished, they were tallied, analyzed and subjected to statistical analysis. For the Academic Performance data, the researcher used the Grade Point Average (GPA) of the students in her class.

The statistical tool utilized in the research were mean and pearson-r. In this study mean was used to measure the stress-vulnerability level and the academic performance among the management students and the pearson-r was used to ascertain if correlation exists between stress vulnerability and academic performance.

III. RESULT

Table 1 is the data of the summary of the level of stress vulnerability among management students of UM Tagum College. The overall mean is 3.12 and described as moderate. The result means that the vulnerability of stress among management students of UM Tagum College is moderately experienced.

TABLE 1. Stress Vulnerability

Indicators	Mean	Description
Family Factors	3.00	Moderate
Financial Factors	3.21	Moderate
School Factors	3.32	Moderate
Environmental Factors	2.96	Moderate
OVERALL	3.12	Moderate

Data presented in Table 2 contains the academic performance result of the management students. The lowest possible rate that a student earned was 75 with a descriptive equivalent of Low and the highest rate was 100 with a descriptive level of very high.

Moreover, professors of UM Tagum College compute the academic performance (GPA) of the students by weighting the following criteria: 30% for the final examination, 10% each for 3 major examination (1st-3rd exam), 15% for research, 10% for Quiz, 10% for Participation and 5% for Assignment.

It is important to ensure that the scaling of the two variables matched, since academic performance originally used 100 scales, converting it to 5-point Likert type is a must. To convert the scale for this variable the researcher used the formula below:

$$F(x) = \log(\text{value})$$

The overall mean for the academic performance of management students was 1.90 and described as low. The result means that the academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College needs immediate improvement.

TABLE 2. Academic Performance

Variable	Mean	Description
Academic Performance	1.90	Low

Table 3 shows the data on the result of the correlation between stress vulnerability and academic performance. Pearson-r was used to determine the significance of the relationship. Since the p-value is more than the .05 level of

significance, the null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. Hence, we can say that there is no significant relationship between stress vulnerability and academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College.

TABLE 3. Correlation between stress vulnerability and academic performance

Paired Variables	r-value	p-value
Stress Vulnerability	.125	.229
Academic Performance		

IV. CONCLUSION& DISCUSSION

The level of stress vulnerability was described as moderate. The following are the specific results of the four indicators under this variable: All of the indicators: school factors, family factors, financial factors, and environmental factors have moderate results. This means that the stress vulnerability among management students of UM Tagum College is experienced. The result affirms the study of Fairbrother and Warn (2003) who emphasized that stress experienced by the students in the school are the following: bombarded homework, student competition (peer pressure), teacher’s failure to monitor student progress, financial constraints, poor relationship with other students, poor teaching strategy, and family problems among others. These stressors were categorized by Taylara (2012) as environmental, financial, family and school factors.

The level of academic performance was low which means that the academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College needs immediate improvement. The result confirms the proposition of Misra et al. (2000) who mentioned that as the students step up every semester, the stress level is predicted to increase due to academic commitments, financial constraints and being preoccupied that lead to poor time management. But to other studies, this increase in stress can be addressed and reduced through effective time management and organized study habits. Misra et al. (2000) emphasized that academic achievement of students shows vital part on becoming effective and efficient graduates which subsequently become an asset in this country which can be beneficial in this nation’s social and economic development. Thus, this issue of low academic performance must be prioritized.

Using Pearson-r to testing the relationship, results did not reject the null hypothesis since the p-value is greater than .05 level of significance. Therefore, we can say that there is no significant relationship between stress vulnerability and academic performance among management students of UM Tagum College. The result of the study debunks the framework of Robbins (1998) expressing that an elevated level of stress or even a moderate sum continued over a significant period, in the long run, incurs substantial damage, and execution decays. The result suggests that other factors aside from stress may contribute to the increase or decrease of the student’s performance. However, it must be noted that sample size isn't sufficient to represent the entire populace; thus, increasing the sample size in future research is highly suggested.

Given the findings of the study, the researcher recommends the following: Foremost, since the level of stress vulnerability is moderate, as much as possible, it must be kept at the lowest level. To lower it down the researcher recommends to conduct the departmental academic competition, this can be initiated at least once every semester wherein there would be an interdepartmental competition to release them from distress while helping them enhance their academic performance. Presented in Appendix A is the enhancement program design for the proposed academic Olympics.

Further, school administrators may give more training to the faculty members through annual retooling particularly addressing communication competency, management of lesson delivery, teaching strategies, and methodologies and classroom management of the faculty. This is suggested to be conducted annually. Moreover, faculty members are also encouraged to improve their work performance by employing new teaching strategies that utilize multiple intelligence like seeing, hearing, kinesthetic or interpersonal. The annual retooling is also suggested to re-train professors on modern ways of teaching that satisfies varied students way of learning.

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